

Supporting Information

Excessive swelling of perfluorosulfonic acid membranes in the context of PEM water electrolysis at elevated temperature and pressure

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1 Experimental setup and primary data

Figure S1 - A schematic of the experimental setup for the membrane treatment at 120 °C and 500 kPa

Figure S2 – Example of selected impedance spectra of AQE87 collected during the experiment (120 °C, 600 kPa) with an illustration of R_{Ω} evaluation

Figure S3 - State of the swollen membranes before and after the hydrothermal treatment (120 °C, 600 kPa, 800 h)

Figure S4 – Resistances of the conductivity cell with **AQE87** sample acquired at 20 °C demonstrating that possible foreign ion contamination is not the cause of resistance increase after the hydrothermal treatment; RP denotes HCl-reprotonated membrane

2 Small/Wide-angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS, WAXS)

For the measurement of SAXS and WAXS, the membranes were sealed in 2mm wide borosilicate capillaries to maintain their hydration conditions (experiments are performed under high vacuum). To account for background scattering, separate measurements of an empty capillary, as well as capillary with water were conducted under identical conditions, so that their contribution could be subtracted from the diffractograms (Figure S5).

Figure S5 – Measured SAXS diffractograms of a) N117; b) F940; c) AQE87; d) AQE98.

The SAXS data were fitted using SASfit software (version 0.94.10, [1]) to obtain positions of the ionomer and crystalline peaks (

Table S1).

Table S1 – Summary of peak positions and corresponding sizes for studied samples *q* and *d* obtained from *x* and *y*, respectively.

		N117		FUMAPEM FS-940-RFS		AQE87		AQE98	
		<i>q</i> / nm ⁻¹	<i>d</i> / nm	<i>q</i> / nm ⁻¹	<i>d</i> / nm	<i>q</i> / nm ⁻¹	<i>d</i> / nm	<i>q</i> / nm ⁻¹	<i>d</i> / nm
As-received	ionomer	1.981	3.172	2.292	2.741	2.155	2.916	2.196	2.861
	lamellar	0.4141	15.17	0.6266	10.03	0.4165	15.09	0.3576	17.57
Activated	ionomer	1.264	4.971	1.227	5.121	1.323	4.749	1.361	4.617
	lamellar	0.3071	20.46	0.1822	34.49	0.2775	22.64	0.2839	22.13
Treated	ionomer	0.5765	10.90	0.2998	20.96	0.4618	13.61	0.7356	8.542
	lamellar	0.1090	57.64	0.0736	85.37	0.0869	72.30	0.1593	39.44

A mass fractal model was employed to describe the overall structure, while a broad-peak function was used to model the two peaks observed in the SAXS curve (corresponding to the lamellar and ionomer structures). In some cases (such as treated F940), the peaks were too small to clearly determine their maxima. In these instances, the standard fitting procedure yielded unrealistically low *q*-values for the peak positions. To address this issue, the regions without peaks were initially fitted using the mass fractal model, after which its parameters were fixed. The remaining curve was then fitted by adjusting only the parameters of the two broad-peak functions. Examples of SAXS curve fitting are shown in **Figure S6**.

Figure S6 – Examples of SAXS curve fitting. a) N117 as-received; b) N117 activated; c) N117 treated; d) F940 treated.

A peak deconvolution was performed for the WAXS data using Fityk software (version 1.3.1, [2]). As the first step, WAXS curves of empty capillary and capillary with water were precisely fitted (shown in **Figure S7a,b**).

One pseudo-Voigt function was enough to describe the curve of the empty capillary, but three Gaussian functions were necessary for the curve of capillary with water. These fits were then used to establish new functions (with 2 parameters – size and position, but fixed shape) used for deconvolution of WAXS curves of studied samples. Two wide amorphous peaks located around 16° and 38° (2θ) have been described by a Gaussian function. A Pseudo-Voigt function was for the remaining sharper peaks related to the crystalline phase. The degree of crystallinity was determined by calculating the ratio of the crystalline peak area to the total area under the WAXS curve (excluding the background – empty capillary or capillary with water). For activated and treated samples, the background contribution of capillary with water is rather high (in many cases accounting for 80% of total intensity), which increases the uncertainty of the calculated degree of crystallinity. Examples of WAXS peak deconvolution are shown in **Figure S6c,d**.

Figure S7 – Examples of WAXS peak deconvolution. a) empty capillary; b) capillary with water; c) as-received AQE98 (in capillary); d) activated N117 (in water).

3 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Membrane samples were analysed by DSC to get more insight into the properties of the water embedded in their structure. Example of such measured thermogram is depicted in Error! Reference source not found..

Figure S8 – Example of measured DSC thermograms (activated N117)

Following equations were used to calculate the distribution of freezing and non-freezing water in the membranes:

$$m_{\text{water,freezing}} = \frac{H_{\text{measured}}}{\Delta H_{\text{fus}}(t_{\text{fus}})} \quad (\text{S1})$$

Where H_{measured} is the heat ascribed to water freezing in the membranes determined experimentally and $\Delta H_{\text{fus}}(t_{\text{fus}})$ is the theoretical enthalpy of fusion at temperature t_{fus} (t_{fus} is also determined experimentally). H_{measured} is an average of the melting and fusion enthalpy, t_{fus} is an average of onset temperatures of fusion and melting peaks from the DSC experiments (

Table S2). $\Delta H_{fus}(t_{fus})$ was calculated from the following equation:

$$\Delta H_{fus}(t_{fus}) = \Delta H_{fus}(0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}) + (C_{p,s} - C_{p,l}) \cdot (t_{fus} - 0) = -333 + (2.2 - 4.2) \cdot (t_{fus} - 0) \quad (\text{S2})$$

Where $\Delta H_{fus}(0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C})$ is the enthalpy of fusion at 0 °C. $C_{p,s}$ and $C_{p,l}$ are the specific heat capacities (at constant pressure) of ice and liquid water, respectively; they were approximated by constant values independent on temperature.

Finally, content of non-freezing water was determined from:

$$m_{water,non-freezing} = m_{water,total} - m_{water,freezing} \quad (\text{S3})$$

Where $m_{water,total}$ was experimentally determined water content from weighing the membranes before and after drying at 120 °C for 3 hours.

Table S2 – Summary of quantitative results from DSC

Sample	Cooling		Heating	
	Onset t / °C	ΔH / J g ⁻¹	Onset t / °C	ΔH / J g ⁻¹
N117 A	-24	16	-14	19
N117 T	-14	62	-18	82
AQE98 A	-19	9	-19	4
AQE98 T	-29	15	-21	17
AQE87 A	-37	4	-23	7
AQE87 T	-33	3	-23	6

4 Atomic force microscopy (AFM)

4.1 AFM of as-received membranes

4.1.1 Experimental details

Bruker cantilevers Scanasyst-air with silicon tip on nitride lever were utilised. Tip apex diameter 2 to 3 nm, spring constant k : 0.4 N m⁻¹. No damage of samples caused by the scanning probe was observed. Resulting images were not further processed except of tilt compensation and flattening.

Each sample was examined on both sides. They are labelled L and R. Labels were assigned without correlation with fabrication process of the sample as it is not obvious to us. Each side was examined at two or three spots.

Range of scan sizes: 10 μ m, 3 μ m, 1 μ m, 350 nm.

4.1.2 Observations

Overview images make it possible to distinguish the membrane fabrication method. Descriptions of images are summarised in the Table S3.

Table S3 - Surface overview - 10 μ m and 3 μ m scan size

Sample	Side L	Side R
N117	Parallel deep grooves	Shallow grooves
F940	Flat surface	Parallel deep grooves
AQE87	Flat surface with fibres up 1 μ m long	Corrugated surface
AQE98	Fig. 30 Corrugated surface	Fig. 35 Parallel grooves. Few fibers up 1 μ m long and debris

Images of 1 μm scan size allow selection of a characteristic location for a detailed examination. Spots without dirt and defects were selected for further imaging. In these places, the fine details of the surface structure can best be explored. Detailed 350 nm images show the surface structure of perfluorinated membranes. In all samples, the surface of the membranes is slightly uneven. In the field of view of 350 nm, the corrugations are at most 5 to 10 nm. The depressions most likely do not mean individual pores.

Non-homogeneous nature of perfluorinated membranes is revealed by adhesivity mapping. The contrast is clear and distinct in comparison with a homogeneous surface. Low adhesivity domains are visible here for each sample and location. Their typical size is given in Table S4. It is possible to observe a correlation - topographically elevated places show lower adhesivity.

The elasticity (modulus) map is also drawn well for most samples and supports information about the non-homogeneous state of the surface. The image is not as clear as with adhesivity. Some inverse correlation to adhesion can be observed.

Table S4 - 350 nm scan size - adhesivity mapping, size of low adhesivity domains

Sample	Side L	Side R
N117	35 – 45 nm	40 – 48 nm
F940	30 – 38 nm, 35 – 40 nm	38 – 48 nm
AQE87	16 – 20 nm	16-25 nm
AQE98	20 – 33 nm, 16 -20 nm	25 -35 nm, 16-20 nm

4.1.3 Conclusion

Aquivion membranes contain fibers. All samples show non-homogeneous surface. Adhesivity domains of size range 16 to 48 nm were observed.

4.1.4 N117 side L

Fig. S9 Overview. Scan size 10 μm . Topography, vertical scale 190 nm

Fig. S10 Overview in 3D.

Fig. S11 Overview. Scan size 3 μm . Topography, vertical scale 25 nm

Fig. S12 a) Scan size 1 μm . Topography, vertical scale 23 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -52 -54 mV.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 248 mArb.

Fig. S13 a) Scan size 350 nm. Topography, vertical scale 6 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 106-187 mV. Domains of low adhesion diameter 35 – 45 nm. Some inverse correlation to topography.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 180 mArb. Some inverse correlation to adhesion.

d) Topography filtered with FFT stopband filter 55 x 55 nm. Vertical scale 2,6 nm. Average distance of neighboring domain 29 nm.

4.1.5 N117 side R

Fig. S14 Overview. Scan size 10 μm . Topography, vertical scale 46 nm

Fig. S15 Overview. Scan size 3 μm . Topography, vertical scale 11 nm

Fig. S16 a) Scan size 1 μm . Topography, vertical scale 6 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -52 -50 mV.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 94 mArb.

Fig. S17 a) Scan size 350 nm. Topography, vertical scale 5 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 88 mV. Domains of low adhesivity diameter 40 – 48 nm. Some inverse correlation to topography.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 85 mArb. Some inverse correlation to adhesion.

4.1.6 F940 side L

Fig. S18 Overview. Scan size 10 μm. Topography, vertical scale 40 nm

Fig. S19 Overview. Scan size 3 μm. Topography, vertical scale 17 nm

Fig. S20 a) Scan size 1 μm. Topography, vertical scale 8 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 91 -250 mV.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 257 mArb

Fig.S21 a) Scan size 350 nm. Topography, vertical scale 8 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 78-259 mV . Domains of low adhesivity diameter 30 – 38 nm. Some inverse correlation to topography.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 325 mArb

Fig.S22 a) Scan size 350 nm. Topography, vertical scale 10 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 51-290 mV. Domains of low adhesivity diameter 35 – 40 nm. Some inverse correlation to topography.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 340 mArb. Some inverse correlation to adhesion.

4.1.7 F940 side R

Fig. S23 a) Overview. Scan size 10 μm. Topography, vertical scale 68 nm

b) 3D overview

Fig. S24 Overview. Scan size 3 μm. Topography, vertical scale 28 nm

Fig. S25 a) Scan size 1 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 15 nm
(R2010)

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 240 -590
mV.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 254
mArb.

Fig. S26 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 7 nm
(R2012)

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 260-590
mV . Domains of low adhesivity
diameter 38 – 48 nm. Some inverse
correlation to topography.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 220
mArb. Some inverse correlation to
adhesion.

4.1.8 AQE87 side L

Fig. S27 a) Overview. Scan size 3 μm . Topography, vertical scale 120 nm

Fig. S28 a) Scan size 1 μm . Topography, vertical scale 16 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -30- 50 mV .

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -22 - 26mV.

c) Overview in 3D. Scan size 3 μm .

c) Modulus, vertical scale 213 mArb.

Fig. S29 a) Scan size 350nm. Topography, vertical scale 9 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -22 -23 mV. Domains of low adhesivity 16 – 20 nm. Some inverse correlation to topography.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 219 mArb no contrast

d) Topography filtered with FFT stopband filter 55 x 55 nm. Vertical scale 4,3 nm. Average distance of neighboring domain 28 nm.

4.1.9 AQE87 side R

Fig. S30 a) Overview. Scan size 10 μm. Topography, vertical scale 150 nm

b) Overview in 3D.

Fig. S31 Overview. Scan size 3 μm. Topography, vertical scale 298 nm

Fig. S32 a) Scan size 1 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 27 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 62 -120 mV.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 195 mArb.

Fig. S33 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 8 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 59-128 mV. Domains of low adhesivity diameter 16 – 25 nm. Some inverse correlation to topography.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 228 mArb . Some inverse correlation to adhesion.

4.1.10 AQE98 side L

Fig. S34 a) Overview. Scan size 10 μm . Topography, vertical scale 108 nm

b) Overview in 3D.

Fig. S35 Overview. Scan size 3 μm . Topography, vertical scale 98 nm

Fig. S36 a) Scan size 1 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 25 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -370 –
-380 mV.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 1100
mArb.

Fig. S37 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 9 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 78 -306
mV. Domains of low adhesivity 20
– 33 nm. Some inverse correlation
to topography.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 440
mArb. Some inverse correlation to
adhesion.

Fig. S38 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 10 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -22 -23
mV . Domains of low adhesivity 16
– 20 nm. Some inverse correlation
to topography.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 360
mArb. Some inverse correlation to
adhesion.

4.1.11 AQE98 side R

Fig. S39 a) Overview. Scan size 10 μm . Topography, vertical scale 139 nm

b) Overview in 3D.

Fig. S40 Overview. Scan size 3 μm . Topography, vertical scale 72 nm

Fig. S41 a) Scan size 1 μm . Topography, vertical scale 21 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 36 -79 mV.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 110 mArb.

Fig. S42 a) Scan size 350nm. Topography, vertical scale 10 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 70-150 mV. Domains of low adhesionity 25 - 35 nm. Some inverse correlation to topography.

Fig. S43 a) Scan size 350nm. Topography, vertical scale 6 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -19-19 mV. Domains of low adhesivity 16 – 20 nm. Some inverse correlation to topography.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 88 mArb.

4.2 AFM of membranes in activated state

4.2.1 Experimental details

Bruker cantilevers Scanasyst-fluid+ with a silicon tip on nitride lever were utilized. Tip apex diameter 2 to 4 nm, spring constant k : 0.7 N m^{-1} . No damage of samples caused by the scanning probe was observed. Resulting images were further processed utilizing tilt compensation and flattening. In some cases, periodic interference was suppressed by filtration in FFT.

Each sample was examined on both sides. They are labelled L and R, corresponding to same sides as in case of the as-received membranes (as-received membrane samples were activated after AFM imaging). Each side was examined at two spots. Range of scan sizes: $10 \mu\text{m}$, $3 \mu\text{m}$, $1 \mu\text{m}$, 350 nm .

4.2.2 Observations

Overview images serve for orientation on the sample. In some cases, insights on membrane fabrication method can be distinguished. Descriptions of images are summarized in the Table S5.

Table S5 - Surface overview - $10 \mu\text{m}$ and $3 \mu\text{m}$ scan size

Sample	Side L	Side R
N117	Shallow grooves	Flat surface
F940	No image due technical problems with fixation of the sample.	Shallow groove, debris on the surface
AQE87	Flat surface with fibres up $1 \mu\text{m}$ long	Corrugated surface
AQE98	Corrugated surface	Few fibres up $1 \mu\text{m}$ long.

1 μm images zoom in on the surface and allow selection a characteristic location for a detailed examination. Spots without dirt and defects were selected. In these places, the fine details of the surface structure can best be explored. Detailed 350 nm images show the surface structure of perfluorinated membranes.

Topography imaging shows the surface of the membranes as a slightly uneven. In the field of view of 350 nm, the corrugations are at most 10 to 20 nm. The depressions most likely do not mean individual pores. The sizes of the observed structures are smaller than those observed on samples in the as-received state.

Adhesivity mapping does not reveal relevant surface structures. As the samples were observed immersed in water, all the capillary forces were eliminated. Attractive Van der Waals forces were too weak to show significant contrast.

The elasticity (modulus) map shows limited contrast. It brings supporting information about the non-homogeneous state of the surface. The image is not as clear as with topography.

The non-homogeneous nature of perfluorinated membranes in swollen state is mainly revealed by topography correlated with elasticity mapping (modulus). Typical size of observed structures is listed in Table S6. It is possible to find a correlation - topographically elevated places show higher modulus. However, in the case of **AQE87** the topography image is not as distinguished as is the correlated image of adhesivity and elasticity.

A special structure was found at **AQE98** at R side. **Fig. S44** and **Fig. S45** show sponge-like structure, rather different from all the other observations.

Table S6 - 350 nm scan size – topography and elasticity mapping, size of lower domains (pits)

Sample	Side L	Side R
N117	12 – 18 nm	10 – 15 nm
F940	No image	22 - 28 nm
AQE87	22 – 28 nm	15-22 nm
AQE98	8 – 25 nm, 16 -20 nm	7 -18 nm, 7-10 nm

4.2.3 Conclusion

Aquivion membranes contain fibres. Samples show slightly corrugated surface in the range 10 to 20 nm. In some cases, non-homogeneous nature can be revealed. Domains of size range 8 to 28 nm were observed.

4.2.4 N117 side L

Fig. S46 Overview. Scan size 10 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 37 nm

Fig. S47 Overview. Scan size 3 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 15 nm

Fig. S48 a) Scan size 1 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 14 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -160 -
150 pN.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 1,5 GPa.

Fig. S49 a) Scan size 350 nm. Topography, vertical scale 10 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -133 – 130 pN. No contrast observable.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 1,4 GPa. Some correlation to topography.

d) Topography filtered with FFT stopband filter 55 x 55 nm. Vertical scale 8,7 nm. Average distance of neighboring domains 22 nm.

Fig. S50 a) Scan size 350 nm. Topography, vertical scale 10 nm

b) 3D image of topography

c) Modulus, vertical scale 1,02 GPa.

4.2.5 N117 side R

Fig. S51 Overview. Scan size 3 μm . Topography, vertical scale 35 nm (R1F008)

Fig. S52 a) Scan size 1 μm . Topography, vertical scale 12 nm (R1t009)

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 220 pN.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 200 MPa.

Fig. S53 a) Scan size 350 nm. Topography, vertical scale 10 nm (R1008)

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 190 pN. No contrast.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 180 MPa. Some correlation to topography.

4.2.6 F940 side L

No image due to technical problems with fixation of the sample. Drift of the sample did not allow to scan the image.

4.2.7 F940 side R

Fig. S54 a) Overview. Scan size 3 μm. Topography, vertical scale 300 nm Debris on the surface.

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 18 nN.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 48 MPa.

Fig. S55 a) Scan size 1 μm. Topography, vertical scale 70 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 2,8 nN.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 226 MPa.

Fig. S56 a) Scan size 350 nm. Topography, vertical scale 18 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 860 pN .

c) Modulus, vertical scale 475 MPa.

4.2.8 AQE98 side L

Fig. S57 a) Overview. Scan size 10 μm. Topography, vertical scale 130 nm

b) Overview in 3D.

Fig. S21 Overview. Scan size 3 μm. Topography, vertical scale 93 nm

Fig. S58 a) Scan size 1 μm. Topography, vertical scale 40 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 420pN.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 225 MPa.

Fig. S59 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 12 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 412 pN.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 280 MPa

Fig. S60 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 10 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 470 pN.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 221 MPa.

4.2.9 AQE98 side R

Fig. S61 a) Overview. Scan size 10 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 199 nm

Fig. S62 Overview. Scan size 3 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 52 nm

Fig. S63 a) Scan size 1 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 30 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 308 pN.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 210 MPa.

Fig. S64 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 17 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 290 pN

c) Modulus, vertical scale 216 MPa

Fig. S65 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 15 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 257 pN.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 212 MPa.

4.2.10 AQE87 side L

Fig. S66 a) Overview. Scan size 10 μm . Topography, vertical scale 190 nm (L2t005)

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -400 - 390 pN.

c) Modulus.

Fig. S67 a) Overview. Scan size 3 μm . Topography, vertical scale 190 nm

Fig. S68 a) Scan size 1 μm . Topography, vertical scale 80 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 1.6 nN.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 685 MPa.

Fig. S69 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 16 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 1,6 nN

c) Modulus, vertical scale 910 MPa.
Some correlation to adhesion

d) Topography filtered with FFT
stopband filter 55 x 55 nm.
Vertical scale 6,5 nm. Average
distance of neighboring domain
25 nm.

4.2.11 AQE87 side R

Fig. S70 a) Overview. Scan size 10
μm. Topography, vertical scale 180
nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 2.2 nN

Fig. S71 Overview. Scan size 3 μm.
Topography, vertical scale 95 nm

Fig. S72 a) Scan size 1 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 32 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 3.2 nN.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 910 MPa.

Fig. S73 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 19 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 1.5 nN

c) Modulus, vertical scale 750 MPa .
Some correlation to adhesion.

4.3 AFM of membranes in excessively swollen state

4.3.1 Experimental details

Bruker cantilevers Scanasyst-fluid+ with a silicon tip on nitride lever were utilized. Tip apex diameter 2 to 4nm, spring constant k : 0.7 N m^{-1} .

Surface of the samples is very sensitive and most observations were not successful due to damage caused by the scanning probe. Repeating scan of the same spot was avoided. Resulting images were further processed utilizing tilt compensation and flattening. In some cases, periodic interference was suppressed by filtration in FFT.

Range of scan sizes: 10 μm , 3 μm , 1 μm , 350 nm.

4.3.2 Results and discussion

Overview images serve for orientation on the sample. Descriptions of images are summarized in Table S7.

Table S7 - Surface overview - 10 μm and 3 μm scan size

Sample	Side X	Side Y
N117	Corrugated surface with debris	No image
F940	No image due damage	No image due damage
AQE87	Corrugated surface with fibres (?) 2 μm long	Corrugated surface with a fiber (?) 2 μm long and debris
AQE98	Corrugated sponge-like surface. Example of surface damage caused by a previous 3 μm scan.	No image

1 μm zoom in on the surface allow selection of a characteristic location for a detailed examination. Detailed 350 nm images show the surface structure of perfluorinated membranes.

Topography imaging shows the corrugated surface of the membranes. In the field of view of 350 nm, the corrugations are at most 19 to 45 nm. The depressions most likely do not mean individual pores. The sizes of the observed structures are bigger than those observed on activated samples. In some cases, the details are better recognized on the 1 μm images.

Adhesivity mapping reveals surface structures. It might be due to visco-elastic behavior of swollen treated surface. The elasticity (modulus) map shows also some contrast.

The non-homogeneous nature of perfluorinated membranes in swollen state is mainly revealed by topography correlated with adhesivity and elasticity mapping (modulus). Typical sizes of observed structures are listed in

Table S8.

Table S8 - 350 nm scan size – topography and elasticity mapping, size of lower domains (pits)

Sample	Side X	Side Y
N117	20 – 35 nm	
F940	No image	No image
AQE87	40 - 50 nm	50 - 60 nm
AQE98	60- 70 nm	No image

4.3.3 Conclusion

Aquivion membrane E87 might contain swollen fibres. Samples are sensitive to damage caused by scanning probe. Samples are corrugated in a range of 19 to 45 nm. The non-homogeneous nature of the surface can be revealed. Then the domains of size range 20 to 70 nm were observed.

4.3.4 N117 side X

Fig. S74 Overview. Scan size 10 µm. Topography, vertical scale 86 nm

Fig. S75 Overview. Scan size 3 µm. Topography, vertical scale 52 nm

Fig. S76 a) Scan size 1 µm. Topography, vertical scale 31 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 18 mV.

Fig. S77 a) Scan size 350 nm. Topography, vertical scale 19 nm

b) Topography filtered with FFT stopband filter 55 x 55 nm. Vertical scale 15,9 nm. Average distance of neighboring domains 29 nm.

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 14 mV.

4.3.5 AQE87 side X

Fig. S78 a) Overview. Scan size 10 μm. Topography, vertical scale 740 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale -51 -132 mV .

c) 3D overview

Fig. S79 a) Overview. Scan size 3 μm. Topography, vertical scale 366 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 106 mV

Fig. S80 a) Scan size 1 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 63 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 395 mV.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 370 mArb.

Fig. S81 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 40 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 16 mV

c) Modulus, vertical scale 47 mArb.

d) Topography filtered with FFT
stopband filter 55 x 55 nm.
Vertical scale 8,1 nm. Average
distance of neighbouring
domain 40 nm.

4.3.6 AQE87 side Y

Fig. S82 a) Overview. Scan size 10 μm. Topography, vertical scale 510 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 256 mV

c) 3D view

Fig. S83 a) Overview. Scan size 3 μm. Topography, vertical scale 366 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 173 mV

Fig. S84 a) Scan size 1 μm. Topography, vertical scale 52 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 52 mV.

c) Modulus, vertical scale 190 mArb.

Fig. S85 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 28 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 34 mV

c) Modulus, vertical scale 140 mArb

4.3.7 AQE98 side X

Fig. S86 a) Overview. Scan size 10 μm. Topography, vertical scale 1414 nm

b) Overview in 3D.

Fig. S87 Overview. Scan size 3 μm. Topography, vertical scale 1650 nm

Fig. S88 a) Scan size 3 μm.
Topography, vertical scale 96 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 800 mV.

Fig. S89 a) Scan size 1 μm .
Topography, vertical scale 524
nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 420
pN.

Fig. S90 a) Scan size 350 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 45 nm

b) Adhesion, vertical scale 14
mV.

Fig. S91 a) Scan size 1000 nm.
Topography, vertical scale 77
nm. Scan made after Fig. 23.

5 References

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